

A RATE-TYPE CRYSTALLIZATION KINETICS MODEL FOR PROCESS MODELLING OF CARBON FIBRE PEEK MATRIX COMPOSITES

Kamyar Gordnian and Anoush Poursartip

Composites Research Network, Department of Materials Engineering, The University of British
Columbia

309-6350 Stores Road, Vancouver, BC, V6T 1Z4, Canada

Email: kamyar@composites.ubc.ca anoush.poursartip@ubc.ca

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we investigate the crystallization behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced PEEK. Both isothermal DSC tests at different target temperatures and non-isothermal DSC tests at different cooling rates are conducted on melted carbon fibre reinforced PEEK tape. Experimental results from different tests indicate that the rate of crystallization is only a function of the state of transformation, i.e., the temperature and degree of crystallinity, and not the thermal history. The results also show the existence of an incubation period or induction time. For induction time in isothermal crystallization, a simple empirical model is adopted from the literature and calibrated with the experimental results. This model, together with the additivity rule is used for prediction of induction time for an arbitrary temperature profile. The rate of crystallization equation and the induction time model are used for prediction of degree of crystallinity at each time instant during processing of carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Process models for composite materials are highly useful tools for understanding the effects of process variables and parameters on the dimensional changes and residual stresses in the final product. Through the use of process models, optimal processing conditions are ensured and production risks and costs are minimized. Process modelling platforms, using sub-model or modular approaches are well established and are being used widely for thermoset composites [1-3]. These sub-models include thermochemical, flow, void and stress models. In recent years, there has been increasing interest in the use of thermoplastic composites for large primary aircraft structures such as fuselage panels. Processing of thermoplastic composites involves heating the material beyond its melting temperature, forming, and then cooling down following different temperature profiles. Whilst cooling down, the material crystallizes and modulus development occurs. The same sub-model approach, applied to thermosets, can be followed for process modelling of thermoplastic composites [4]. The main component of a thermochemical, or perhaps more suitably called thermophysical, sub-model for thermoplastics is the crystallization kinetics model.

Poly (ether-ether-ketone), PEEK, is a semi-crystalline high performance thermoplastic featuring high impact resistance, excellent solvent resistance and high glass transition temperature (143°C) [5]. These properties make PEEK a viable replacement for epoxy matrices in aerospace applications. Different isothermal and constant cooling rate non-isothermal crystallization models are available in the literature [7].

Isothermal crystallization of semi-crystalline polymers is typically studied using the Avrami equation [6]:

$$X_{vc} = X_{\infty} [1 - e^{-kt^n}] \quad (1)$$

where X_{vc} is the absolute volume fraction of crystallinity, X_{∞} is the final value of crystallinity, k is the kinetics constant, n is the Avrami exponent and t is the process or crystallization time.

Most crystallization kinetics models for non-isothermal crystallization are extensions of Avrami equation [7]. For example, Ozawa [8] considered the simple case of constant cooling rates and modified Avrami equation as:

$$1 - \frac{X_{vc}}{X_{\infty}} = e^{-\frac{\chi_c(T)}{a^m}} \quad (2)$$

where a is the cooling rate, $\chi_c(T)$ is the cooling rate function and m is Ozawa exponent. Ozawa showed that Eq. (2) can be used to predict the degree of crystallinity of PET in constant cooling rate experiments. Eq. (2) needs the values of crystallinity for different cooling rates at each target temperature and is restricted to constant cooling rate conditions and is therefore not suitable for process modelling [7].

A generalization of Avrami equation was suggested by Nakamura *et al* [9] as:

$$X_{vc} = X_{\infty} \left[1 - e^{-\left(\int_0^t K(T) dt\right)^n} \right] \quad (3)$$

Kamal and Chu [10] introduced a similar integral Avrami equation as:

$$X_{vc} = X_{\infty} \left[1 - e^{-\left(\int_0^t k(T) n t^{n-1} dt\right)^n} \right] \quad (4)$$

Applying isothermal conditions, Eq. (3) and Eq. (4) reduce to the original Avrami model. It was shown by Patel and Spruiell [7] that both Nakamura and Kamal models overpredict the non-isothermal crystallinity data for nylon 6. It is possible to express both models in a differential or rate-type form which is more useful for process modelling [7]. In the differential form of Eq. (4), the rate of transformation depends explicitly on time and therefore is not suitable for prediction of crystallinity during processing. The differential form of Eq. (3) is superior as the rate of transformation is only a function of temperature and the amount of transformation; however, it still overpredicts the results. The primary reason for this is not accounting for the induction time or incubation period [7].

As reported in the literature [11,12], PEEK exhibits double melting peaks in calorimetry depending on the crystallization conditions making traditional Avrami based models unreliable for prediction of crystallinity during processing. Velisaris and Seferis [13] suggested a model by considering two separate Avrami type crystallization processes in parallel. This model is based on the integral Avrami expression of Eq. (4). Recently Bessard *et al* [14] introduced a similar dual mechanism model by combining two differential forms of Eq. (3) instead.

In this work, we present a differential, or rate type, model for prediction of crystallinity of melt crystallized carbon fibre PEEK matrix composites during processing. The rate of crystallization is a separable function of temperature and degree of crystallinity. Its temperature dependence is modelled by an exponential function of reciprocal undercooling. No model is considered for its crystallinity dependence; rather the model-free approach espoused by Vyazovkin is used [15]. In order to account for the nucleation process, a simple empirical model is adopted [16] for induction time in isothermal cases and is extended to non-isothermal cases. It will be seen that the experimental results are in good agreement with the model predictions.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The material under study is Tencate Cetex® TC1200 PEEK AS-4 unitape which is reinforced with 59% of carbon fibres by volume. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was used for investigating isothermal and non-isothermal crystallization of the material. Experiments were conducted using a TA Instruments Discovery DSC machine on samples of about 10 mg. In both isothermal and non-isothermal tests, the specimens were heated up to 400°C and held isothermal for 10 minutes to clear all crystallinity history of the material.

Isothermal temperatures were considered between 305°C and 325°C. The samples were cooled down rapidly from molten state to each target temperature and held isothermal until crystallization was complete. In non-isothermal experiments, test samples were cooled down with cooling rates between

1 °C/min to 10 °C/min to room temperature. The heat flow curves for one isothermal and one non-isothermal case are shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively.

Figure 1: Isothermal DSC heat flow at 320 C

Figure 2: Non-isothermal DSC heat flow at 5 CPM

Assuming proportionality between the crystallization rate and the heat flow and integrating the peaks shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 and using the enthalpy of fusion for a perfect crystal (130 J/g [13]), mass fraction of crystallinity during the process can be calculated. Mass fraction of crystallinity is converted to volume fraction of crystallinity using the densities of the amorphous phase and crystalline phase [13].

Figure 3: Isothermal crystallization experimental results

Figure 3 illustrates the degree of crystallinity (volume fraction of crystallinity) versus time, obtained from isothermal experiments for four different temperatures. It can be seen that the maximum degree of crystallinity is almost the same for all crystallization temperatures in the investigated

temperature range ($X_{max} \approx 0.33$). The results show that an induction time or incubation period exists, which is higher for higher temperatures. Also the higher the crystallization temperature, the slower the crystallization speed is.

Variations of crystallinity with temperature for non-isothermal experiments with different cooling rates are shown in Figure 4. It is observed that similar to the isothermal results, maximum degree of crystallinity is about 0.33 for all cooling rates. The results also show that crystallization starts and ends at lower temperatures for higher cooling rates.

Figure 4: Non-isothermal crystallization experimental results

3 MODELLING

Differential form or rate type models are more desirable for process modelling, as the transformation rate is expressed in terms of process parameters (or state variables) and there is no path (history) dependency. These process parameters are temperature, T , and degree of crystallinity, X , in a crystallization process.

For investigating the temperature dependence of crystallization rate, iso-conversional curves can be extracted from both isothermal and non-isothermal test results. Figure 5 illustrates $\ln\left(\frac{dX}{dt}\right)$ versus $(T_m - T)^{-1}$, extracted from isothermal tests for different temperatures and non-isothermal tests at different cooling rates, for $X = 0.1$ and $X = 0.2$, respectively ($T_m = 343^\circ\text{C}$). It can be seen that isothermal and non-isothermal results overlay reasonably well and there is no significant difference in crystallization mechanisms.

Figure 5: $\ln\left(\frac{dX}{dt}\right)$ versus $(T_m - T)^{-1}$ for $X = 0.1$ and $X = 0.2$

Similar results are obtained for other values of degree of crystallinity. This implies that the crystallization rate can be expressed as:

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = K(T)f(X) \tag{5}$$

where

$$K(T) = K_0 e^{-\frac{E}{R(T_m - T)}} \quad (6)$$

The parameters in Eq. (6) are calculated from a family of iso-conversional curves like the curves in Figure 5 for different values of degree of crystallinity. In each iso-conversional curve, the slope of the line and the intercept give the values of $-\frac{E}{R}$ and $\ln(K_0 f(X))$ respectively. The results for a family of iso-conversionals are plotted in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Figure 6: $-\frac{E}{R}$ versus X

Figure 7: $K_0 f(X)$ versus X

In order to be able to predict the crystallinity using Eq. (5), we need to know the time for onset of crystallization or the induction time. Godovsky and Slonimsky [16] proposed a simple empirical model for the isothermal induction time in melt crystallization as:

$$t_i = t_m (T_m - T)^{-c} \quad (7)$$

where t_m and c are material constants and T_m is the equilibrium melting temperature. By fitting this equation to induction times measured in isothermal experiments and assuming $T_m = 343^\circ\text{C}$ and $t = 0$ at T_m , t_m and c are evaluated. The values are reported in Table 1 (assuming T and T_m are both in $^\circ\text{C}$ or K and t_i is in mins).

t_m	c
2.591×10^5	3.269

Table 1: Fitting parameters for Eq. (7)

The values of induction time versus temperature from different isothermal experiments are compared with model predictions in Figure 8. We observe that the simple empirical model of Eq. (7) fits very well to the experimental results.

Figure 8: Induction time values for isothermal crystallization

For non-isothermal experiments, the additivity rule [17] is used. The additivity rule states that the total time required to reach a specific amount of crystallinity can be obtained by adding the fractions of time elapsed to reach that amount isothermally, until the summation becomes equal to 1, i.e.,

$$\int_0^{t_i} \frac{dt}{t_i(T)} = 1 \quad (8)$$

In Eq. (8), t_i is the induction time and $t_i(T)$ is the isothermal induction time at temperature T , obtained from Eq. (7). Figure 9 compares the experimental results and model predictions for non-isothermal experiments at different cooling rates. It can be seen that the model predictions are very accurate. According to [17], additivity is valid when the instantaneous rate of transformation is a function of temperature and the amount transformed only. Therefore, the results from Figure 9 show that Eq. (5) is a suitable model for crystallization behaviour of this material.

Figure 9: Induction time values for non-isothermal crystallization

Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) are used with the data from Figure 6 and Figure 7 and the induction times calculated using Eq. (7) and Eq. (8) for prediction of the degree of crystallinity at each time instant of the process. Figure 10 compares the experimental and modelling results for four different temperatures in the isothermal case. Similar results are presented in Figure 11 for non-isothermal crystallization.

Figure 10: Isothermal crystallization-Experimental and modelling results

Figure 11: Non-isothermal crystallization-Experimental and modelling results

Figure 10 and Figure 11 show that the proposed model is capable of predicting both the onset of crystallization and crystallization growth. The modelling approach is unified for both isothermal and non-isothermal melt crystallization. Also the onset of crystallization or induction time for non-isothermal experiments is evaluated using the isothermal results and matches the experimental measurements.

The proposed modelling approach can be extended to other crystallization temperatures and cooling rates and also to cold crystallization. This is the subject of ongoing research.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Isothermal and non-isothermal melt crystallization of carbon fibre reinforced PEEK composites were studied using DSC experiments. Experimental results show that, in the investigated (and relatively narrow) range of temperatures and cooling rates, the maximum degree of crystallinity is almost constant for all isothermal and non-isothermal tests. A rate type modelling approach was presented which is capable of predicting the degree of crystallinity during processing. The onset of crystallization was predicted using a simple empirical model from the literature and the additivity rule. Model predictions are in good agreement with experimental results.

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